

Some Studies on Glass-bonded Zircon Ceramics

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Several body compositions were prepared by incorporating zircon in a porcelain composition where all the felsper was replaced by glassy frit. Apparent porosity, modulus of rupture, spalling resistance etc. were measured which showed improvement in fine ceramic bodies due to zircon incorporation.

Porcelain occupies a very important position because of its manifold applications. For improving certain thermochemical characteristics addition of refractory components is made. A considerable amount of work¹⁻⁶ has been carried out on zircon porcelains as high density and high frequency ceramic materials. In the present investigation attempts have been made to improve the properties of porcelain by incorporating zircon.

Results and Discussion

The batch composition of the samples are given in Table 1. The results of chemical analyses are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1—BATCH COMPOSITION AND DRYING SHRINKAGE OF THE SAMPLES

Sample no.	Batch composition (% w/w)				Linear shrinkage %
	China clay	Quartz	Glass powder	Zircon	
I	40	15	15	30	0.262
II	40	10	15	35	0.485
III	40	5	15	40	0.582
IV	40	—	15	45	0.750

TABLE 2—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF THE INGREDIENTS

Constituents	China clay wt%	Quartz wt%	Glass powder wt%	Zircon wt%
SiO ₂	46.06	98.0	72.65	35.01
Al ₂ O ₃	28.26	0.62	1.05	—
ZrO ₂	—	—	—	63.87
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.43	0.51	0.15	0.35
CaO	0.26	—	9.6	—
MgO	—	—	1.70	—
Na ₂ O+K ₂ O	—	—	14.05	—
LOI	13.36	—	—	—

The results of apparent porosity, modulus of rupture and true density as a function of temperature are presented in Figs. 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Drying shrinkage (Table 1) was within 1% and this is the reason of no. significant dimensional change which is very much required for this type

Fig. 1. Variation of apparent porosity with temperature. (O) I, (×) II, (Δ) III and (□) IV.

of bodies. It is seen that shrinkage was a direct function of ZrO₂ content.

Firing shrinkage (Table 3) is found to be a direct function of temperature. Maximum shrinkage was observed with sample no. I and minimum with IV. From the result it appears that the flux had undergone reaction with the other components to a significant extent. In sample nos. II and III the interaction rate of glass powder and quartz was comparatively slow, and as the quartz content decreased, the rate increased. The values were within the limits to cause any defect in the body and as such neither any crack nor any significant distortion was observed. Thus the effect of composition was much prominent when glass powder was used as a fluxing material.

Fig. 2. Variation of modulus of rupture with zircon content at different temperatures: (O) 1000, (x) 1100, (Δ) 1200 and (\square) 1300°.

Fig. 3. Variation of density with temperature: sample no. (O) I, (x) II, (Δ) III and (\square) IV.

From Fig. 1 it is seen that the variation of porosity with temperature is irregular from 1100 to 1200°, the change being not very much beyond which a sharp fall in the porosity value was noticed in all the cases. Again with the increase of zircon content in the mixture, the apparent porosity decreased which clearly indicated that in this temperature region zircon reacts in a greater way than quartz.

From Fig. 2 it is seen that the values of modulus of rupture were quite comparable with that of

TABLE 3—FIRING SHRINKAGE (LINEAR %) AND THERMAL SHOCK RESISTANCE* OF SAMPLES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Sample no.	1000°	1100°	1200°	1300°
I	3.65 (14)	4.78 (10)	5.89 (9)	7.33 (7)
II	2.33 (14)	3.95 (11)	4.84 (9)	5.95 (7)
III	2.38 (14)	3.55 (11)	4.54 (10)	5.38 (8)
IV	1.22 (14)	2.32 (12)	3.31 (10)	4.37 (8)

*Thermal shock resistance data in parenthesis.

other hard porcelains. ZrO₂ increased the mechanical strength to significant extent which was related to the formation of crystalline phases, i.e. zircon mullite and their orientation and interlocking. Minimum strength was noticed with sample no. IV at 1300°. From the above results it appears that by keeping the content of the flux fixed at 15%, more zircon can be incorporated in the composition.

From Table 3 it is observed that zircon improves the thermal shock resistance when it replaces quartz. Again the glass powder used as a flux did not remain in free state which might be the cause of high thermal shock resistance.

It can be noted from Fig. 3 that in all the compositions, maximum density value achieved at 1100° and it was found to be directly related to the ZrO₂ content in the mixture (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Variation of density with zircon content at different temperature: (O) 1000, (x) 1100, (Δ) 1200 and (\square) 1300.

From the analysis of the data obtained from various testing, it may be concluded that zircon can be better incorporated in fine ceramic bodies in which glass powder is used as a flux.

Experimental

Raw china clay, quartz powder, zircon sand and soda lime-silica glass were selected as raw materials. The raw materials were ground to -100 mesh. The body composition was selected in such a way that in each case the proportions of clay and glass powder were kept fixed. But the zircon content was gradually increased at the expense of quartz.

The required quantities of the raw materials were milled for about 4 h under wet condition using 80% water on total weight of the batch. The slip was then evaporated to dryness and the dried mass was kneaded properly with little water whereby a semi-stiff plastic mass was obtained for fabrications. Rectangular bars of identical dimensions were fabricated and dried at room temperature (30-32°) for 24 h followed by drying at 110° for another 24 h. The samples were then fired in the furnace at the rate of 5° per min upto 600° and then the heating rate was increased to 10° per min to the desired temperature for firing. The soaking period at each temperature was kept fixed for 2 h.

Testing methods :

The rectangular bars were marked at the two extreme ends before drying. The distance between the two marks was measured before and after drying by travelling microscope from which percent linear shrinkage was calculated. The length of the bars before and after firing was measured by travelling microscope from which firing shrinkage was calculated.

The samples were placed on a ring of definite size fitted at the lower plate of the apparatus. A sharp edged knife was fitted at the upper plate. Pressure was slowly and uniformly applied till the point of failure. Modulus of rupture was calculated from the gauge reading by the following formula,

$$M = \frac{3Wl}{2bd^2}$$

where, M is the modulus of rupture, W the breaking load, b the breadth of the sample, d the depth of the sample, and $l=2$ inch.

Thermal shock resistance test was performed by introducing the sample in the furnace (700°) into the firing zone and kept for 10 min, then taken out and immersed in water for 10 min and again introduced into the furnace. This operation was repeated until the first crack developed at the surface.

Porosity and true density were measured following standard procedures.

References

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